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The role of expert credit agencies in the development of modern international trade

Abstract

An Expert Credit Agency, which provides information, assessments and ratings affecting the financial decisions of businesses, investors and governments, plays an important role in a modern global economy. The role of expert credit agencies in the modern international economy, their impact on financial markets and their future development will be analyzed in this article.

The role of ECA in interaction on financial markets: ECAs provide assessments of the creditworthiness of various entities: from corporations to entire states. These assessments affect loan rates, the ability to attract investment, and even international relations. ECA ratings set standards and enable investors and lenders to make more informed financial decisions.

Keywords: ECA, states, credit, market, export, investments, support, decision, finance, processes, business.

Introduction

In the evolution of globalized economies, expertise credit agencies have a crucial role to play. They provide information on the attractiveness of investment in different regions and countries, assess the credit worthiness of companies and countries, and issue ratings to help investors and lenders make informed decisions. In international financial markets, ECAs play an important role in improving transparency and predictability. Rating agencies assist market participants in understanding the risks associated with investing and lending in different countries through their issuance of ratings. It represents an important contribution to developing international relations and strengthening trust among actors in the global economy.

The main services of export credit agencies are: provision of export loans for the purchase of

goods and services by foreign partners, financing projects abroad, insurance, guarantee of exports and export credits, private investment insurance abroad, provision of information and consulting services, provision of grants and participation in projects aimed at implementing socially significant tasks in the field of ecology, energy efficiency and energy saving, medicine and healthcare, as well as the protection of the rights and freedoms of citizens. In order to enhance the activities of national undertakings, export credit agencies provide services on a preferential basis supporting national exports. Activity ECA in the field of credit and investment insurance contributes to the formation of favorable conditions for the development of global trade and Capital movements across borders, activations. [2] The entrepreneurial activities of the national companies increase in exports and investments as well as maintaining global stability financial system. By improving transparency and predictability in capital markets, credit reporting agencies are also playing an important role for the development of international finance relations. The risk associated with investments and loans in various countries is explained by their assessments to market participants.

Results

They are expected to keep improving their processes and methods, given the challenges faced by European Competent Authorities with respect to transparency and objectivity. The quality and objectivity of assessment can also be improved by further technological developments and the application of big data, which contribute to more effective functioning of global finance markets.

First, in the area of lending and financing there are important functions carried out by expert credit agencies. It carries out an assessment of the credit worthiness of enterprises and individuals, provides advice on financing issues as well as helps to develop and implement Financial Strategies. They thus play an important role in business development, promoting investments and developing international trade.

Secondly, in support of developing international cooperation and the integration of economies from across countries, it is vital that expert credit agencies take an active role. By providing support to projects and undertakings abroad, it helps improve the availability of financial resources. It also contributes to raising the volume of trade, investment and creating favorable financing conditions for business development. [4]

Moreover, important institutions

that influence financial markets and regulate the international financial system are expert credit agencies. They have carried out credit risk analysis and assessment, developing standards and tools for the evaluation of creditworthiness to help reduce risks as well as improve Financial Stability. Export strategy or programs for developing domestic exports are implemented by the majority of trading countries around the world and represent a significant part of their National Foreign Trade Policy. The history of the country's involvement in international labor market division, a type of territorial government structure, sector specific national export characteristics and current and future economic objectives shall be taken into account when drawing up programs and strategic documents. These factors also play a decisive role in determining the targets and particular activities carried out by National Programs and Export Support Strategies.

The main goals of ECA:

Expanding the geography of supplies of traditional and new products;

Indirect support for the development of priority industries;

Reducing risks when financing commercial;

Projects by private banks and when carrying out foreign trade in complex;

Economic, social and political conditions that may be accompanied by force majeure and crisis phenomena in economy, as well as attracting additional resources to the country's economy.

As specialized state, semi-state or state-authorized private financial institutions - ECAs that support exports include the implementation of large and particularly significant government projects, such as export-import banks, investment and insurance agencies, and insurance companies. The creation of the ECA was mainly driven by growth in international trade and structural changes: a more diverse share of technical, capital intensive products; processes of regional integration and globalization of the world economy as well as an increasing importance for export income to support national budgets. [3] The activities of the ECA at the present stage occupies a special place in the system of state support for the economy and exports, which is due to the growth and complication of macroeconomic problems, the unstable global general economic and commodity conditions, increased risks of global development and

international competition, as well as the low efficiency of many other institutions and mechanisms for supporting national economy. Analysis of the functioning and volume of support provided by ECA in developed and dynamic developing countries in the period after the financial and economic crisis of 2008-2009 confirms that ECAs have become an even more significant factor in shaping the international competitive environment and influencing trade flows. Thus, in 2012, leading ECAs carried out more than 447 transactions totaling \$117.9 billion, which is 52% more than in 2011.[2]

Discussion

Against the backdrop of global financial and economic crises, the problem of developing and implementing effective industrial policy in many countries is becoming more urgent, which determines two approaches in this area: radical liberal and traditional. The radical liberal approach denies any industrial policy in the national economy and adheres to the theory of solving all economic problems by the correlation of supply and demand in conditions of self-regulation of the market. However, some critics point to possible conflicts of interest in the activities of such agencies, since their income may depend on how actively businesses, banks, investors and governments seek their services. Such conflicts of interest may affect the objectivity and reliability of the ratings and assessments provided.

The traditional approach involves administering the economy through the use of subsidized incentive mechanisms. The most succinct relationship between the concepts of “state”, “politics” and “industry” is expressed by L.A. Tikhomirov: “A real, strong system of the country’s economy can only be developed on the idea of developing production forces. This is a system of economic independence of the country, the completeness of all its forces, extracting and processing, harmoniously complementing each other and resulting in an economically self-affirming country” and approaches to defining the concept of “industrial policy”, directly or indirectly reflecting the role and functions of the state in the economy and shaping the directions of its implementation.[1]

Nevertheless, there are some problems and criticisms of the ECA's activities. Some experts point to potential conflicts of interests as, in the case of agencies' revenues; it is possible that client requests are influenced by their activity. The objectivity of the rating and evaluation carried out by ECAs may be affected. In the case of financing exports,

international experience has shown that commercial banks are not prepared to take on a part of these risks. In parallel, the creation and development of specialized financial institutions that cover these risks has been necessitated by growing international competition and a large number of promising emerging markets with an increased risk for trading in them. These institutions, in their capacity as ECAs, finance exports on behalf of the State and with its support. As part of the implementation of state support for exports and the protection of private investments, specialized Institutions whose aim is the application of a variety of mechanisms For the purpose of selling national goods and services The favorable conditions of foreign markets as a result of increased competition from other countries, The expansion of trade in luxury goods The time frame for implementation of the investments has been extended projects. These bodies are export credit agencies ECAs.

Comparisons are made between the main economic parameters of the ECA's activities, their organizational and legal structure, the services they provide and the results of the work to support exports. As a result of the global financial and Economic Crisis, emerging trends and directions for foreign ECA's activities are revealed. Government support for exports has emerged as a leading direction in the context of industrial policy itself during the global financial and economic crisis and after, with increasing attention from foreign countries to the implementation of a comprehensive, innovation oriented industrial policy.[5]

Export activity is the key factor for boosting production dynamism and competitiveness in industry as well as supporting a country's position on the global economy if manufacturing is the driving force behind Modern Economic Growth. Currently, specialized state, semi-state and non-state institutions have been created and operate in more than 100 countries around the world, authorized to provide financial and non-financial support to exporters.

Conclusion

Indeed, it is vital that professional credit agencies play their part in the 21st century international economy. They help to provide the data and analytical information needed for financial decisions worldwide, playing an important role within the framework of a globally interconnected financial system. The ECAs should, however, make further efforts to improve their processes and methodologies in order to ensure that they retain the confidence

of their customers as well as a higher priority is given to transparency and objectivity when providing ratings and evaluations. In addition, the possibilities of trends in economic development and finance markets that may be beneficial for stakeholders to develop Sustainable Development strategies are illustrated by experts from credit agencies. These companies provide a valuable tool to investors, businesses and government agencies with analyses and reports on the current situation of different industries and sectors of the economy.

For this reason, the professional credit rating agencies play a significant role in providing stability, effectiveness and development of today's global economy. In order to cope with the rapid development of global market conditions, it is vital that they keep improving their practices and continue to be a tool for financial sustainability and development.

ECAs can also help reduce information asymmetries and increase confidence in financial markets by providing market participants with a better understanding of risks and opportunities. This contributes to the development of the effective functioning of the market economy as a whole. However, challenges to transparency and objectivity remain significant, and credit reporting agencies must continually improve their processes and methodologies to maintain the trust of clients and the public. Maintaining a high standard of ethical conduct and impartial judgment has become increasingly important in the rapidly changing global economic environment. In turn, improving the quality and objectivity of an expert credit agency assessment can help to enhance the efficiency of international finance markets through further advances in technology and use of large data. Overall, the expert credit agencies are an important element of the global financial system and will continue to be a vital part of international financial relations in spite of their challenges and criticisms.

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